

randomized trials, one for each cross. Analysis of the basic generations (P_1 , P_2 , F_1 , F_2 , B_1 , and B_2) and F_3 families of these crosses showed that each of these characters was heritable. The narrow-sense heritabilities of 1,000-grain weight and the number of empty spikelets panicle⁻¹ were high (0.77-0.97), and those of grain yield plant⁻¹ were low (0.17-0.18) in both crosses.

The proportion of recombinant inbred lines that could be extracted by SSD from each cross, the performance of which was better than that of the best parent, was predicted using information obtained from F_3 families. While only 3% of these lines were expected to achieve this target for panicle weight and number of grains panicle⁻¹ in the first cross, the expected proportion of superior lines was higher (8-82%) for other characters in both crosses. The actual proportion of the 100 F_6 lines produced by SSD from each cross, the performance of which was equal to or better

than the desired target, was close to that predicted for most characters.

Furthermore, estimates of the genetic correlation between characters (obtained from the SSD lines) indicated that most of these correlations were less than 0.5. Where they were larger, this was generally favorable to the breeder. Exceptions were from the expected correlations between, for example, grain yield and its components. Both of these pedigrees, therefore, had considerable potential in their ability to produce superior recombinant inbred lines. This was not only for their single character performance, but also for the desired multiple phenotype.

The average performance of the lines produced by the conventional methods was higher in both crosses than that of the SSD lines for grain yield plant⁻¹ and number of grains panicle⁻¹. Comparison of the best lines produced by each of the four methods for each character, however, showed that little difference existed between them for

grain yield or its components. The effect of the selection carried out during inbreeding with the P, MP, and BL methods was to cull low-yielding genotypes rather than to retain high-yielding material, despite attempts to do so.

The average per line cost of producing the best SSD lines was only US\$13.70 compared with US\$89.50 for the P method, US\$69.70 for the MP method, and US\$22.30 for the BL method. The SSD method is also more rapid if three generations can be raised per annum at high densities in the nursery.

These results are consistent with quantitative genetics theory, which indicates that attempts to carry out indirect selection visually of characters of low to intermediate heritability during inbreeding are unlikely to be successful. It is better to defer selection until homozygous material can be raised in a randomized trial in which characters of interest can be measured directly. ■

A promising dwarf rice mutant induced through gamma irradiation

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M01.20-19-4 (IET13981) is a dwarf medium-duration mutant, developed

through gamma irradiation of local rice cultivar Chettivirippu. This cultivar is tall and susceptible to lodging. Its average yield is 2.5 t ha⁻¹, and it is highly resistant to brown planthopper, stem borer, gall midge, blast, sheath blight, and sheath rot. The mutant is shorter, more resistant to lodging, and higher yielding than the parent variety (see table).

We selected plants up to the M_1 generation, after which the stable mutant, M01.20-19-4, was included in yield trials (see table).

M01.20-19-4 is suitable for cultivation in all of the rice-growing seasons of Kerala, and the people prefer its red grain.

The mutant will be proposed for release shortly. ■

Characteristics, comparative grain yield and pest and disease scores of mutant M01.20-19-4 and parent variety. India, 1989-94.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Productive tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Av (yield t ha ⁻¹)						Insect-disease score (0-9)					
				CYT ^a (3 seasons) 1989-90	RRS Mon-compu (4 seasons) 1990-92	MLT ^b		AICRIP ^c trials		Brown plant-hopper	Gall midge	Stem borer	Blast	Sheath blight	Sheath rot
						Research stations (5 locations) 1992	Farmers' fields (9 locations) 1992	(17 locations) 1993	(16 locations) 1994						
M01.20-19-4 (IET13981)	98	120	7	4.2	3.5	4.6	5.2	4.8	4.4	2.2	2.8	2.2	2.8	1.5	1.9
Chettivirippu	120	110	5	2.7	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.7	2.9	2.6
M05	-	-	-	-	2.9	3.6	4.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ratna	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.0	4.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ptb33 (resistant check)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.1	2.5	3.5	2.1	2.0	2.0
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.0	9.0	8.5	9.0	9.0	8.0
CD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.42	0.40	ns	0.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aCYT = comparative yield trial with 7 entries. ^bMLT = multilocation trials with 7 entries. ^cAICRIP = All India Coordinated Trials; 1993, 68 entries; 1994, 64 entries.